

Electrochem 2019

AMEND

CONTINUE

Submission ID

44

Title

Atomic layer deposition thin films from Al_2O_3 and HfO_2 as protection of commercially pure titanium for biomedical applications

Abstract

In this study we focused on the deposition of Al_2O_3 and HfO_2 films on commercially pure titanium (CP-Ti) to explore their effect on corrosion properties of CP-Ti under simulating physiological solution. Atomic layer deposition (ALD) was explored as a preparation method using a trimethylaluminium as a precursor for Al_2O_3 , and tetrakis(ethylmethylamido)hafnium(IV) as a precursor for HfO_2 films. The film thickness was around 150 nm. CP-Ti samples were prepared in two different ways: (i) grinding using 500-grit SiC emery papers and (ii) grinding followed by polishing using silica suspension. Chemical composition analysed using time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy analysis using focused ion-beam system confirmed the presence of stoichiometric Al_2O_3 and HfO_2 films.

Electrochemical measurements were carried out in Hanks' physiological solution at 37 °C. Both samples, Al_2O_3 and HfO_2 ALD-coated CP-Ti, exhibited for ca. 5 orders of magnitude lower current density in the passive region than bare CP-Ti, as shown by potentiodynamic polarization curves. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements confirmed that ALD Al_2O_3 and HfO_2 films on CP-Ti reached large impedance values at low frequencies, ca. $10^9 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ after 1h immersion in electrolyte. Only in the case of HfO_2 films on ground titanium surface the values were smaller, slightly below $10^8 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$. Additionally, at prolonged immersion up to 40 days only ALD Al_2O_3 and HfO_2 films on polished titanium surface retained good barrier properties. Accordingly, films deposited on polished surface exhibit higher protection against corrosion than the films deposited on ground surface.

Authors and Affiliations

Ivan Spajic (Presenting)

Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia
Jožef Stefan International Postgraduate School, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Ingrid Milošev

Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Permission to publish